

Supplementary Material

for

A CALPHAD assessment of the Ga–In–Sn liquidus for designable low-melting liquid-metal coolants

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Method

The liquidus surface was mapped on a 1,275-point composition mesh spanning the ternary simplex (0.02 mole fraction step), each point scanned over a 121-step temperature sequence, for approximately 154,000 Gibbs energy minimizations per surface. The two surfaces (Muggianu extrapolation and fitted assessment) together required approximately 308,000 evaluations. Combined with the binary phase-diagram scans (501 composition points, 220 temperature steps each) and the isopleth scans (roughly 400 composition steps at 800 temperature values each), the total workflow executed approximately 1.1 million equilibrium evaluations in roughly 30 minutes of wall clock time on a consumer laptop (AMD Ryzen 7, 16 GB RAM, pycalphad 0.10, 8 threads). Earlier assessments of ternary liquidus surfaces, carried out without automated composition scanning, typically sampled 10 to 30 compositions, a density insufficient to resolve isotherm curvature close to the eutectic.

Data and code availability

The following files are included as supplementary material and are deposited in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21038087>):

GaInSn.tdb	Unfitted Ga-In-Sn database (Muggianu, no ternary term)
GaInSn_fitted.tdb	Fitted Ga-In-Sn database (L = -8000 J/mol ternary parameter)
InSn_David2004.tdb	In-Sn binary database (David et al. 2004, reproduced for completeness)
scripts/fit_gasn.py	Nonlinear least-squares fit of Ga-Sn Redlich-Kister parameters
scripts/fit_ternary.py	Ternary parameter fit to Evans and Prince eutectic temperature
scripts/tern_fitted.py	Ternary liquidus surface calculation (fitted, 1275-point mesh)
scripts/tern_full.py	Ternary liquidus surface calculation (unfitted Muggianu)
scripts/make_paper_figs.py	Binary phase diagrams and isopleths (Figs. 1-3, 8)
scripts/run_pbsn2.py	Pb-Sn control calculation

scripts/refine_tern.py High-resolution eutectic finder (0.25 °C temperature step)
scripts/sensitivity_check.py Sensitivity table (Table 3 of main text)

All scripts require Python 3.10+, pycalphad ≥ 0.10 , numpy, scipy, and matplotlib, available via conda-forge. Run each script from the directory containing the TDB files and the scripts/ subdirectory. The high-resolution ternary grids (tern_fitted_grid.npy, tern_full_grid.npy) are generated by tern_fitted.py and tern_full.py and are also provided as pre-computed CSV files for direct reuse.